

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 1.5 Recommendations for CDR

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Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at the EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

This report has been developed in collaboration between the author and editor below.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon Dioxide Removals (CDR) are indispensable to the EU’s climate objective and to achieve negative emissions after 2050. According to [modelling](#) results from the European Commission (EC), the achievement of the EU climate-neutrality objective will require the industrial carbon capture of 200-350 MtCO₂ through direct air capture and bioenergy with CCS. On 30 November 2022, following the Communication on Sustainable Carbon Cycles, the EC published a proposal on an [EU regulatory certification framework for carbon removals](#).

In this context, ZEP has set up a Carbon Removal Working Group, and has successfully executed several initiatives. The scope of the Temporary Working Group and recommendations that resulted from the collaboration between its participants are described in this report.

2 TEMPORARY WORKING GROUP ON CARBON DIOXIDE REMOVALS

2.1 TWG CDR Objectives

The focus of the working group is to:

- Support the EC/DG RTD on its work related to the CDR Mission Innovation.
- Follow and provide input to the CDR Mission, ensuring that its programme and activities are aligned with key messages from ZEP and IWG9 reports and recommendations.
- Provide updates to the ZEP Advisory Council, ACEC, and Networks on the Missions’ activities.

Moreover, to streamline ZEP’s work related to CDR, it was proposed to extend the scope of the working group to the following objectives:

- Follow the EC’s upcoming proposal on certificates for carbon removals and provide input as appropriate.
- Develop further the ZEP position on CDR.
- Follow and support ZEP’s participation in the expert group on carbon removals.
- Follow the development on carbon accounting methodologies, voluntary markets, article 6 of the Paris Agreement, and the needed regulatory frameworks.

2.2 Working Timeline

The TWG has started working on the extended scope objectives in December 2022, with a kick-off meeting on 13 December. The table below presents the original proposed timeline, with milestones and key dates related to the EU policy timeline:

Presentation of the Terms of Reference for endorsement at the ZEP ACEC (M1)	22 November 2022
EC proposal on the certification of carbon removals	30 November 2022

Kick-off meeting under new, extended, scope (M2)	13 December 2022
Presentation of the Terms of Reference for approval at the 73rd ZEP AC (M3)	14 December 2022
Kick-off meeting of the EC expert group on CDR	December 2022
Report on CDR, article 6 and the needed regulatory framework (M4)	H2 2023

2.3 Working Group Participants

The TWG is co-chaired by Filip Neele (TNO) and Nils Røkke (SINTEF). The group includes participants directly involved in Mission Innovation’s CDR Mission, namely Gassnova and the EC’s DG RTD.

The work under the extended scope is supported by the existing participants, as well as experts on carbon removals from NGOs, industry and research organisations. The TWG is made up of almost 40 participants working for companies based in Norway, Belgium, The Netherlands, France, Germany, Greece, the UK and the US.

2.4 Key questions

As the political recognition of the importance of CDR increases, along with support and deployment, the following set of guiding questions has steered the efforts of the working group:

- Should CDR certificates be traded in the EU ETS? Is so, under what conditions?
- How should CDR certificates be allowed to be used?
- Are there learnings to be taken from voluntary carbon markets where CDR certificates are traded?
- Are there regulatory and funding gaps or opportunities that need to be addressed?
- How should CDR be best incentivised? Is there a need to develop the business case/increase public support?
- Are current carbon accounting methodologies appropriate for CDR projects?

3 EU CERTIFICATION FRAMEWORK FOR CARBON REMOVALS

While emission reduction remains fundamental to limit the global average temperature increase to below 1.5 °Celsius, the deployment of carbon removal practices and strategies will be necessary to mitigate the impact of residual emissions. To that end, the proposed EU's certification framework will play a crucial role for achieving climate neutrality by 2050, ensuring credibility in certifying carbon removals through strict **quantification, additionality, long-term storage and sustainability** criteria (QU.A.L.I.T.Y criteria). By setting high certification methodologies standards, the regulation aims at combatting greenwashing, fostering innovation while guaranteeing the authenticity of certified carbon removals for a sustainable future. Its scope will cover permanent carbon storage, carbon storage in products, and carbon farming activities.

3.1 ZEP Response to the Call for Feedback on the EU CRCF

ZEP welcomed the European Commission's initiative to establish a certification framework for carbon removal activities. In response to the call for feedback on the EU CRCF, ZEP provided a [set of recommendations](#) aimed at ensuring the establishment of an effective framework.

3.1.1 Storage timescales

ZEP welcomed the inclusion of a definition of “permanent carbon storage” in the proposal. However, we highlighted the need for clear timeframes and clear communication on the risk of reversal across different carbon removal activities. We suggested the following timescale:

- Thousands of years for permanent storage in geological reservoirs.
- Decades to centuries for carbon storage in products and carbon farming.

We also recommended the different timescales and risks of reversal to be included in the minimum information required in a certificate, as listed in Annex II of the proposal.

3.1.2 Defining carbon removals

In a [report](#) published in 2020, we introduced the four principles that must be met for any practice or technology to be commonly considered as achieving Carbon Dioxide Removal:

1. Carbon dioxide is physically removed from the atmosphere.
2. The removed carbon dioxide is stored out of the atmosphere in a manner intended to be permanent.
3. Upstream and downstream greenhouse gas emissions, associated with the removal and storage process, are comprehensively estimated and included in the emission balance.
4. The total quantity of atmospheric carbon dioxide removed and permanently stored is greater than the total quantity of carbon dioxide emitted to the atmosphere.

ZEP has voiced concerns about the proposed definition of carbon removal, noting that it encompasses activities solely resulting in carbon reductions. We therefore called for a more robust and thorough definition based on the aforementioned principles.

3.1.3 Clarifying eligibility criteria

To provide predictability for developers and investors, ZEP expressed the need for more clarity on which activities qualify for certification, especially concerning blue economy solutions and waste-to-energy facilities. We recommended the capture and storage of biogenic CO₂ in the waste-to-energy sector to be recognized as a removal activity, thereby unlocking important revenue streams for waste management activities and enabling the industry to deliver on its large removal potential.

Additionally, we called for greater flexibility to incorporate new technological solutions within the certification process, as well as more clarity on the integration of carbon removal activities involving trans-boundary value chains. In this respect, ZEP also recommended that a mechanism for the (mutual)

recognition of high-quality storage sites be put in place and applied for the purposes of certification as well as accreditation under the EU ETS.

3.1.4 Quality criteria

High-level QU.A.L.I.TY criteria are essential to ensure that certified activities generate real carbon removals with accurately quantified environmental benefits, in line with sustainability objectives. We stressed that the certified CO₂ removals must be based on a robust, transparent and complete quantification methodology (see principle 3 in the section 2.1.2. ‘Defining carbon removals’). To ensure that projects deliver real carbon removals, ZEP highlighted that the quantification of the net carbon removal benefit should take into account the inherent differences between technological and nature-based solutions, particularly with regards to the compliance of the activities with the additionality criteria.

In order to achieve ambitious net-zero and net-negative goals, rapid and substantial scaling of removal efforts is essential. ZEP suggested building on existing carbon accounting methodologies (such as GHG quantification in the Innovation Fund) to avoid duplication and accelerate support for carbon removals within the EU. In addition, once the methodologies are developed for each activity, we have proposed to adopt a phased implementation approach.

Overall, we strongly advocate for the establishment of robust standards for removals permanence, carbon accounting, as well as Monitoring, Reporting and Verification. In line with this commitment, we published a [report](#) in 2021 specifically addressing carbon accounting for carbon dioxide removal.

3.1.5 Usage of certified carbon removal units

While ZEP welcomes the European Commission's commitment to investigate and provide guidance on how permanent carbon removals could be integrated into the EU carbon market, as set out in the provisional agreement on the revision of the EU ETS, we have stressed the need for greater clarity on the allowed uses of carbon removal units certified under the EU framework.

3.1.6 Interaction with other frameworks

ZEP recognized the unique opportunity for the proposed EU framework to establish itself as a global standard in carbon removal. With this perspective, we have emphasized the significance of sharing knowledge and experiences to facilitate the development and implementation of similar international approaches. We have stressed the importance of establishing clear and precise carbon removal definitions, principles, and methodologies, which are essential to ensuring support for quality removals aligned with net-zero goals. In line with this, ZEP reaffirms its commitment to actively support the necessary efforts to strengthen the proposed framework.

3.2 EU Expert group on carbon removals

Instrumental in advancing the Commission's work on the voluntary certification of carbon removals, the Expert Group assists in the preparation and implementation of policy initiatives and related legislative proposals in the field of carbon removals, facilitates extensive collaboration among stakeholders,

advocates for high-standard certification criteria, and ensures alignment with EU regulations. The Group held three meetings in 2023:

- First meeting: Kick-off on March 7th, 2023
- Second meeting: Focus on Carbon Farming held on June 21st-22nd
- Third Meeting: Concentration on Industrial Carbon Removals held on October 25th-26th.

The ZEP representative in the Expert Group, Kristin Jordal from SINTEF attended the first and third meetings in Brussels, and participated partially in the second meeting online.

3.2.1 Consultant Consortium's Input and Technical Scoping Paper Overview

DG CLIMA enlisted a dedicated consortium on consultants (ICF, Fraunhofer and Cerulogy) to support its work in addressing industrial removals methodologies. Ahead of the third meeting, the Expert Group members received a [Technical Scoping Paper](#) outlining the pertinent EU regulatory framework, detailing existing industrial carbon removal methodologies, and highlighting distinctions among existing standards. The paper comprehensively lays the groundwork for future endeavours in crafting EU certificates methodologies for carbon removals, offering insights into the existing regulatory framework, including the CSS Directive, the EU ETS Directive, and the Renewable Energy Directive.

The period for submitting comments on the Technical Scoping Paper ended on November 10th, and was submitted to the ZEP TWG on Carbon Removal. The Working Group did not submit any comments, resulting in no feedback being provided by the ZEP.

3.2.2 Identified Gap in the EU ETS Directive

The existing framework does not account for the possibility of biogenic CO₂ being transported from capture to storage facilities. Consequently, under the current EU ETS rules, emission allowances must be surrendered in the event of CO₂ leakage (e.g., during loading/offloading from ships; trucks; or trains), regardless of whether the leaked CO₂ originates from biomass, air, or the ocean.

ZEP's representative, Kristin Jordal, suggested amending the directive to make the surrender of emission allowances mandatory only for fossil CO₂ included in the EU ETS. Regarding certified CO₂ from biomass, air, or the ocean categorized as carbon removals, a solution could involve introducing a buffer system or a similar approach. For instance, certificates could represent less than the total captured CO₂ eligible as carbon removals, creating a buffer to balance any leakages.

3.2.3 Modular Methodologies

During the third Expert Group meeting, two examples of Industrial Carbon Removal methodologies were presented: Direct Air Carbon Capture and Storage (DACCS) by Climeworks, and BioEnergy Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS) by Stockholm Exergi. Following the presentation, it was stressed that certificates should be tailored to specific projects, and the Certification Framework should adopt a "modular" approach.

ZEP's representative recommended a clear definition for the "Certificate Module for industrial carbon removal", emphasizing its compatibility with other modules within the Certification Framework. This clarity would enable different stakeholders to develop methodologies adhering to the Framework's standards.

Additionally, ZEP suggested acknowledging the diverse methods of achieving Carbon Removal through the industrial use of biomass, encompassing various sectors such as waste-to-energy, cement, metal production, pulp and paper, and potentially segments within the food industry. This underscored the importance of modularity in BECCS-related carbon removal certification methodologies. As an illustration, we emphasized the necessity of including a dedicated module for biochar production, highlighting its potential application in metal production processes.

Even though the topic was not explicitly discussed, the methodologies should be adaptable to accommodate Direct Ocean Capture in the future. There is ongoing research and innovation activities directed towards reducing CO₂ emissions from oceans. If such technologies become viable, there is potential for synergies with offshore carbon storage.

3.2.4 Carbon Emissions Reduction

It is crucial not to lose sight of the primary climate objective: reducing carbon emissions. Industrial Carbon Removals will only constitute a fraction of the future need for CCS activities. ZEP needs to continue communicating this position. Moreover, according to Kristin Jordal, it might be pertinent for ZEP to explore whether a more precise definition can be articulated regarding the hard-to-abate emissions that necessitate compensation through carbon removals.